

The Influence Of The Discovery Learning Model for the Result of IPS Subject Grade V UPTD SD 124385 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

The background to this research is based on observations made by researchers in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar, where teachers still use conventional learning models, resulting in low student learning outcomes. From the problems that exist in the class, it is necessary to find a solution, namely by applying the *Discovery Learning learning model*. This learning model is suitable for use in all subjects and this model is suitable for use in class V because this learning model invites students to find their own conclusions from learning. This research used a pre-experimental method with a One Group *Pretest-Posttest* design with a sample of 25 students. Based on the results of the power analysis test used, the Hypothesis Test results obtained were $T = 15.469$ and $T_{table} = 2.064$ with $T_{count} > T_{table} = 15.469 > 2.064$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. With this explanation, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Discovery Learning* learning model on student learning outcomes in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Based on Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System states that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals and the skills needed for himself, society, nation and state. The purpose of education is to guide the nature that exists in children, so that they can achieve the highest safety and happiness. Education is something a person wants to achieve to reach a higher point. Education is the learning of knowledge, skills, and habits of a group of people that is passed from one generation to the next through teaching, training, or research. The definition of education is simplified, namely as a learning process carried out so that students are more active in participating in learning.

According to Ihsana (2017: 4) learning is an activity where there is a process from not knowing to knowing, not understanding to understanding, not being able to becoming able to achieve optimal results.

According to Hernawan (2013:9) learning is an activity carried out to help students learn good lessons. Learning is assistance provided by educators so that the process of acquiring knowledge and knowledge can occur, as well as forming attitudes. Learning can be simplified as a way for teachers and students to carry out learning interactions.

Learning media are tools used by teachers to convey learning to students. The importance of this learning media for teachers and students plays a very important role in increasing students' interest in learning because when using learning media in the classroom students become interested in participating in the learning that takes place in the classroom. The use of this media also makes learning in the classroom become real.

Educators have an important role in improving the quality of human resources to realize general welfare and can realize the ideals of the Indonesian nation in making the nation's life intelligent. Therefore, education initiates educated human resources who are able to face increasingly advanced developments. Education is seen as a very useful process in life which is not merely a preparation for continuing to higher education, but education plays an important role in preparing quality human resources.

According to Honson (2014:6) *Discovery Learning* is a model for developing an active way of learning by discovering it yourself, investigating it yourself, so that the results obtained will be faithful and long-lasting in your memory. This media will enable students to seek more of their own knowledge based on the experience gained by each individual because this media is student-centered.

According to the researcher's experience from Field Experience Practice (PPL) activities at UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar, the results showed that it is important for a teacher to use the right learning model to facilitate the teaching and learning process carried out in the classroom so that the learning carried out becomes more active. Currently, elementary schools are using the 2013 curriculum.

Based on activities carried out by researchers, at UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar, the total number of teachers is 11 people, including 1 principal, 6th grade teacher, 2 religion teachers, 1 English teacher, and 1 administrator. The total number of students is 130 students. The school address is Jalan Sawi No. 2, Tomuan Pematangsiantar.

However, the researcher found that the problem that the researcher encountered during the observation was the use of learning models that were not varied or conventional so that the learning process was not effective. The delivery of

learning material is less interesting due to the lack of use of learning media, resulting in low learning outcomes. In the learning process in class V, the teacher still uses the lecture method. As a result of using this method, students' activities during learning are only as listeners to explanations from the teacher and taking notes on things they consider important. Students are less active in the learning process and tend to be passive because the center of learning is in the teacher, not the students.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In research implementation activities, the theoretical framework contains theories related to the research title Theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs Subtheme 2 Humans and the Environment in learning 3 Ethnic and Religious Diversity in Indonesia in Class V. Students are expected to be more courageous in discovering their respective opinions so that students' learning outcomes are better. This conceptual framework can be depicted in the concept map below:

METHOD

Explain your methodology in this chapter. You should explain your research instruments, data collection processes, data analysis processes or hypothesis testing processes, and data display processes .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

This research was carried out to determine whether or not there was an effect of a treatment, namely by using the *Discovery Learning learning model* carried out by researchers on student learning outcomes using Theme 1 Subtheme 2 at UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar. The subject in the research that the researcher created was class V. The learning delivered by the researcher in conducting experiments during the research was using Theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs Subtheme 2 Humans and the Learning Environment 3 Ethnic and Religious Diversity in Indonesia, with social studies learning content. However, before carrying out the research, the first step taken by the researcher was to test the test instrument. Where, the instrument test was carried out in the same class, namely class V, with a different school with 35 questions. This instrument test was carried out at UPTD SD Negeri 125543 Pematang Siantar. From the instrument tests carried out, results were obtained where of the 35 questions tested, there were 25 questions that were included in the valid category and 5 questions that were invalid. There were 25 questions declared valid. So, what will be used during *the Pretest* and *Posttest* during research in the class under study is 25 questions.

The researcher carried out the learning by giving *pretest questions* , the function of which was to determine the students' level of knowledge. Then the researchers will analyze the pretest answers that have been given. Then the researchers conducted learning using the *Discovery Learning learning model* . After being given treatment, the researcher gave *posttest questions* using the same questions as *the pretest* which functioned to determine the level of students' abilities after being given treatment.

First, a data normality test is carried out, where the normality test is used to determine whether the collected research data is normal or not. This normality test uses SPSS 21 with a significance level of > 0.05 , the results of the pretest normality test which obtained 0.351, the data is said to be normal because $0.351 > 0.05$ and the posttest normality test obtained $0.113 > 0.05$, so the data is said to be normal. After carrying out the normality test, a homogeneity test is then carried out where the data homogeneity test is used to determine whether the research data collected is homogeneous or not according to the specified criteria, significance > 0.05 , a significance value of 0.361 is obtained, so it is said that what was tested is homogeneous because $0.361 > 0.05$. Next, an N-Gain score test is carried out, where the N-Gain score test is used to determine the effect of learning outcomes before and after learning with predetermined categories. So, an N-gain of 0.56 is obtained in the medium category, so it can be said that there is an influence on student learning outcomes. After carrying out the N-Gain score test, a t test was carried out, where this t test was used to find out whether there was an influence of the *Discovery Learning learning model* on student learning outcomes. The t test shows that $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$, namely $15.465 > 2.064$ and/or significance of $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the *Discovery Learning Learning Model* on Social Studies Learning Theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs Subtheme 2 Humans and the Environment in Class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar.

Tabel 1. Hasil Uji t

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
POSTTEST - PRETEST	20.72000	6.69900	1.33980	17.95479	23.48521	15.465	24	.000

Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine whether or not there was an influence of the *Discovery Learning Learning Model* on student learning outcomes in Theme 1 Subtheme 2 class V. A *t test* was carried out with the help of SPSS 21 and the *t* count was obtained. 15,465 . Based on the *t* table of $df\ n-1 = 24$ at a significance level of 0.05, the *t* table value is 2.064. The results show that the calculated *t* value $>$ *t* table is $15.465 > 2.064$ or significant $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that "There is an influence of the *Discovery Learning Learning Model* on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class V Students in Theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs Sub-theme 2 Humans and the Environment in learning 3 Ethnic and Religious Diversity in Indonesia UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar". In other words, the hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

Based on the discussion of the results of this research, it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of class V students in the *Pretest* and *Posttest* were very influential after the students received the *Discovery Learning learning model treatment* . This can be seen from the average *Pretest score* of 69.84. And the average value of the *Posttest* is 83.08. The results of hypothesis testing in the Paired Sample *T-Test* with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and a *t* table of 2.064 with a calculated *t* of 17.321. Thus, $t\ count > t\ table$, namely $15.465 > 2.064$, so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So from the test results it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Discovery Learning learning model* on student learning outcomes in Theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs Subtheme 2 Humans and the Environment in learning 3 Ethnic and Religious Diversity in Indonesia in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

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